

ESCALATOR Communication Strategy

Code of Conduct

Link: <https://escalator.sadilar.org/conduct/>

All events, communication will be governed by the [SADiLaR Code of Conduct](#).

Email

The official email address for ESCALATOR is escalator@talarify.co.za with the SADiLaR representative menno.vanzaanen@nwu.ac.za.

Website

Link: <https://escalator.sadilar.org>

Repository: <https://github.com/anelda/escalator-sadilar>

The website is built on the [Academic template](#) using [Hugo](#). It is accessible via [Github](#) and deployed through [Netlify](#).

Language policy

All communication will be done in English. Guest blog posts may be placed in any of South Africa's 11 official languages and will be translated into English (budget permitting). Guest posts should be useful to the community by:

- Advertising opportunities accessible to South African researchers and students
- Explaining how to use tools that are relevant to DH/CSS or Humanities/Social Sciences in general
- Describing open data sets that are accessible to South African researchers and students
- Describing training resources that are accessible to South African researchers and students and so forth.
- And more...

Twitter

Link: <https://twitter.com/DHCSSza>

A new Twitter account has been created [@DHCSSza](#).

Slack

DHCSS Slack workspace where anyone can join (the space is governed by the [Code of Conduct](#))-
https://join.slack.com/t/escalator-workspace/shared_invite/zt-och1644m-sAf71_NzqyGFVwbyV2svlw

Blog

Link: <https://escalator.sadilar.org/post/>

Regular features (starting 1 June 2021)

- Monthly (week 1): project update
- Monthly (week 2): a summary of interesting blog posts/articles from the community
- Monthly (week 3): miscellaneous
- Monthly (week 4): contribution from the SADiLaR team

Ad hoc

- Tools
- Events
- Opportunities
- Feedback
- Resources
- Guest posts (actionable)

YouTube Channel

Link: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCcLjFCG2SNzZhxUJZyLcLg/playlists>

ESCALATOR established a YouTube channel where all recordings and other relevant content will be shared to improve findability and accessibility for the community. Community members are encouraged to let us know when good and relevant content becomes available.

Zenodo Community

Link: <https://zenodo.org/communities/escalator/?page=1&size=20>

All project documentation, presentations, and other relevant materials will be uploaded to our Zenodo space and will be shared under open licenses such as the [Creative Commons 4.0 license](#).